

A New Leucoanthocyanin from *Moringa oleifera* Gum

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Moringa oleifera syn. *M. pterygosperma* is reputed for its medicinal uses¹. Survey of chemical literature shows that no phytochemical investigation has been undertaken on its stem gum although the presence of different chemical compounds in its seeds, flowers and leaves, has earlier been reported². Our investigation on the stem gum has led to the isolation of a new leucoanthocyanin characterised as leucodelphinidin-3-O-β-D-galactopyranosyl(1→4)-O-β-D-glucopyranoside.

Acetone extract of the gum was fractionated into water-soluble and water-insoluble fractions. Extraction of the latter with ethyl acetate yielded a compound, molecular formula, C₂₇H₃₄O₁₈, m.p. 158°d, R_f 0.37 (tlc; C₆H₆-EtOAc, 1 : 1, v/v), λ_{max} (EtOH) 282 nm. It gave a positive Molisch's test and negative test with aniline hydrogen phthalate reagent³ indicating it to be glycosidic in nature. The glycoside gave different shades of colour with EtOH/HCl, EtOH/FeCl₃, ammonium molybdate/acetic acid, ammonia and vanillin-HCl, indicating the glycoside to be a leucoanthocyanin.

The glycoside on complete acid hydrolysis with 20% methanolic hydrochloric acid gave two sugars galactose and glucose (identified by co-p.c., m.p., optical rotation and crystalline derivatives) along with an anthocyanidin identified as delphinidin by colour reactions, paper chromatography, λ_{max} (EtOH) 556, 450 nm, λ_{max} (EtOH-AlCl₃) 582 nm⁴ and comparison with an authentic sample of delphinidin isolated from the fruit coat of *Solanum melongena*⁵. Partial acid catalysed hydrolysis of the glycoside with 4% methanolic hydrochloric acid resulted in the preferential removal of galactose (paper chromatography) followed by glucose showing the galactose moiety to be terminal and the glucose linked glycosidically with the aglycone. Enzymic hydrolysis⁶ of the glycoside with emulsin afforded galactose, glucose and the aglycone showing the presence of β-linkage between the two sugars and also between the disaccharide and the aglycone.

The acetate of the glycoside, m.p. 128°d, C₂₇H₂₁O₁₈-(COCH₃)₁₃, and its methyl ether (with only phenolic hydroxyl methylated), m.p. 102°d, C₂₇H₂₉O₁₃(OCH₃)₅, suggested the presence of five phenolic and eight alcoholic hydroxy groups in the molecule. Alkaline cleavage of the methylated glycoside gave trimethylphloroglucinol and dimethylgallic acid indicating the presence of free hydroxyls at C₅, C₇, C₃, C₄ and C₅. The methylated glycoside on acid hydrolysis gave an anthocyanidin, λ_{max} (EtOH-HCl) 530 nm, corresponding to pentamethyldel-

phinidin. The hypsochromic shift⁷ of 26 nm suggested the substitution of all the free phenolic hydroxyls. Thus it could be concluded that the sugar is not linked at either of the positions C₅, C₇, C₃, C₄' and C₅'. The only alternative left is the 3,4-diol group. The glycoside got polymerised on prolonged acid treatment⁸, whereas the completely methylated glycoside lacked this property indicating thereby the position of sugar moieties at position-3 of the diol group. No formation of free sugar on catalytic hydrogenation⁹ (Pt/H₂) of the glycoside, showed that C₄ benzylic hydroxyl is not involved in the sugar linkage. Had the sugar been linked at benzylic C₄ hydroxyl¹⁰, the glycosidic linkage would have been cleaved. The suggested biogenesis of this type of compound also favours position C₃ for glycosidic linkage. It was therefore concluded that the two sugar moieties are linked as disaccharide at position C₃ of the diol group. The failure of the glycoside to reduce Fehling solution and to give a positive test with aniline hydrogen phthalate reagent indicated that both the sugars galactose and glucose are linked through their respective reducing groups.

To find out the position of inter-sugar linkage, the methylated glycoside with all the phenolic hydroxyls methylated was subjected to quantitative periodate oxidation¹¹. Only 3.02 moles of oxidant were consumed with the concomitant formation of 1.01 moles of formic acid per

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mole of the methylated glycoside. These results indicate the position of inter-sugar linkage as (1 → 2) or (1 → 4) and also that the sugar is present as a disaccharide in pyranose form. Had the terminal monosaccharide unit been in furanose form no formic acid would have been liberated.

In order to prove whether O-2 or O-4 of the glucose moiety is involved in the linkage, the glycoside was ex-

haustively methylated¹² and subsequently hydrolysed. The hydrolysate was fractionated on Whatman no. 3 paper using butanol-acetic acid-water (5 : 1 : 4, v/v) as developing solvent, and 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose (TMG) as reference. Quantification by alkaline hypiodite showed their presence in equimolar ratio. 2,3,4,6-Tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose¹³, $-R_{\text{TMG}}$ 0.88, m.p. 72–73°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{32} + 43^\circ$ (acetone), these building units must have arisen from the D-galactosyl end-groups; 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose¹⁴, $-R_{\text{TMG}}$ 0.81, m.p. 121–23°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} + 69^\circ$ (water); 1,4-bis-*p*-nitro-benzoate, m.p. 186–88°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} - 32^\circ$ (chloroform), these must be linked through O-1 and O-4.

Therefore the evidences indicate that the disaccharide is present as galactosylglucose having the (1→4) inter-sugar linkage and it is linked to the aglycone through the O-1 of glucose.

The glycoside could therefore be designated as leucodelphinidin-3-*O*-β-D-galactopyranosyl(1→4)-*O*-β-D-glucopyranoside. The suggested structure was in conformity with its spectral data : ν_{max} (KBr) 3 450 (OH), 1 614, 1 505, 1 462 (aromatic ring), 1 260, 1 155, 1 040 and 820 cm^{-1} (sugar moiety); δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 6–7 (12H, m, sugar protons), 5.80 (1H, m, 3-H), 5.04 (1H, m, 2-H), 4.78 (1H, m, 4-H), 3.87, 3.80 (2H, each d, 6- and 8-H, $J_{6,8}$ 2.3 Hz), 2.80 (2H, d, 2'- and 6'-H).

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